

UTILIZATION OF WEB BASED LIBRARY SERVICES (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SNSCE LIBRARY)

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Abstract:

The present study was examined the utilization of web based library resources and services. All the respondents are aware about web based library resources and services and the main purpose of the utilization of web based library resources and services for their academic purpose. All the respondents are frequently used and enjoyed the benefits for knowing current development in their subjects.

Key Words: WWW, Digital Library Services, Web Based Library Services & SNSCE (SNS College of Engineering)

1. Introduction:

WEB is popularly used as the synonymous term of World Wide Web or Internet or online. The web is a client or server system used to access all kinds of information to anyone on the net. The information can be in the form of regular text, hypertext, pictures, sounds, newsgroups and other types of data. To access this information, use a client program called browser. Within the web, the information is stored in pages. Each page can hold not only information but links to other pages. In each page a particular word or sequence of words highlighted item and the other information related to that words in some other pages. A digital library service (web based library) manages and develops electronic services, different search engines, directory, meta-search engines, gateways, subject portals electronic journals and online databases each type could be used in a different way, from simple keyword searching up to peer-reviewed web sites.

2. Objectives of the Study:

- The study aims to,
- ✓ To determine the availability and awareness of web based information resources and services in SNSCE library.
 - ✓ To know the utilization of web based information resources and services and usefulness in teaching and learning process among the faculty members in SNS College of Engineering, Coimbatore District, and Tamil Nadu.

3. Methodology:

For the purpose of the data collections, structured questionnaires were designed. The stratified random sampling technique was used in administrating the questionnaires and interview with the engineering professionals in SNSCE.

4. Review of Literature:

Many scholars, researchers and information scientists have contributed a lot of research publications on utilization of information technology in library and information science and library management. Hence, a review of a few studies deserve due attention for the analysis of the present study. Lohar and Kumbar (2008)¹ conducted a survey at Jawaharlal Nehru National College of Engineering Library, Shimoga (Karnataka) to find out the use of CD_ROMS and Internet resources and services. The study also covers the impact of these resources on the student academic work/study. Also describes the problems faced in using the electronic resources. A survey of 110 undergraduate and post graduate students of different disciplines was conducted through questionnaire. Finally, it is concluded that the main intention using CDs and internet resources and services has been the academic interest of the student community. Babu et. al. (2010)² examined the uses of internet resources by the academic community of the Sri Venkateswara University (SVU), Tirupati. For this purpose a survey was carried out using questionnaire tool. The results show that users from all branches of science are making use of Internet resources better than social sciences and humanities. Providing training to its users at the beginning of each semester will improve its use and reduce the problems faced by the library users. They also highlighted the various problems and an issue involved in handling digital library and has given suggestions to improve the library services to meet the demands of the users. Thanuskodi and Ravi (2011)³ examined the use of the Internet by the members of social science Faculty of Annamalai University. The results indicate that the use of Internet services by the faculty members is associated with an increase in the number of research papers and with improvement in the quality of research and teaching. According to Margam Madhusudhan (2011)⁴ "web-based OPACs of IIT libraries and their ILMS venders should the possibility of

integrating features such as Federated search, Meta search functionality, faceted navigation, visual map, the most popular, ranking, word cloud and refine menu.

5. Findings:

The analysis has been made for selected 200 respondents, which included 100 male and 100 Female respondents with regard to gender and 30 professors, 50 Associate Professors and 120 Assistant Professors with regard to designation from SNSCE.

5.1 Frequency of Accessing Web Based Resources and Services: The findings of designation-wise distribution of respondents frequency of accessing web based resources and services reveal the fact that, 67.79 percent of Professor respondents access web based resources and services more than once in a week, 55.33 percent of Associate Professor respondent's access web based resources and services more than once in a week and 50.71 percent of Assistant Professor respondent's access web based resources and services more than once in a week.

5.2 Time spent of Accessing Web Based Resources and Services: The findings of the designation-wise distribution of respondent's time spent of accessing web based resources reveal the fact that, 36.26 percent of Professor respondents, 43.93 percent of Associate Professor respondents and 40.22 percent of Assistant Professor respondents spend two hours per day for accessing web based resources and services.

5.3 Most Commonly Used Browser: The findings of the designation-wise distribution of respondents most commonly used browser reveals that 77.14% Professor respondents 79.59% Associate professor respondents use Internet Explorer and 67.38% Assistant professor respondents use Google chrome. The findings of the gender-wise distribution of respondents most commonly used browser reveal that, 70.38% male and 87.38% female respondents use Internet Explorer and Google chrome respectively.

5.4 Frequently Used of Search Engine: The findings of the designation-wise distribution of respondent's frequent use of search engine reveal that, 80.70 percent of Professor respondents, 82.95 percent of the Associate Professor respondent's and 93.76 percent of Assistant Professor respondents use Google search engine. The findings of the gender-wise distribution of respondents frequent use of search engine reveal that, 87.84 percent of the male respondents and 93.69 percent of the female respondents use Google search engine.

5.5 Format Preferred to Download Articles: The findings of the college-wise distribution of respondents format preferred to download articles reveal the fact that, 50% respondents preferred PDF format 14.38% respondents preferred HTML 28.77% respondents preferred word format and 6.85% respondents preferred other format for downloading articles. The findings of the designation-wise distribution of respondents format preferred to download articles reveal the fact that, 51.34% professor respondents preferred PDF format, 40.00% Associate professor respondents preferred PDF format and 53.90% Assistant professor respondents also preferred PDF format for downloading articles. The findings of the gender-wise distribution of respondents format preferred to download articles reveal the fact that, 50.47% male respondents and 48.72% of female respondents preferred PDF format for downloading articles.

5.6 Purpose of Using Web Based Resources and Services: The findings of the designation-wise distribution of respondent's purpose of using web based resources reveals the fact that 86.55 percent of professors use web based resources for keeping up-to-date information, 81.40 percent of Associate Professors use web based resource for publishing articles and 88.28 percent of Assistant Professors use web based resources for research. The findings of the gender-wise distribution of respondent's purpose of using web based resources reveal the fact that, both male (83.58%) and female (77.34%) respondent's use web based resources for research purposes.

5.7 How the Library Help to Use Web Based Resources and Services: The findings of the college-wise distribution of respondents how the library help to use web based resources and services reveal that, 26.85% respondents opinion that instruction in library to use web based resources and services; 32.19% respondents opinion that notification of new resources; 23.97% respondents opinion that library helps for easier access and 16.99% respondents opinion that library helps in other way to make use of web based resources and services. The findings of the designation-wise distribution of respondents how the library help to use web based resources and services reveal that, 33.56 percent of the Professor respondents opinion that notification of new resources; 31.33 percent of the Associate Professor respondents opinion that same-notification of new resources and 34.04 percent of the Assistant Professor respondents opinion that instruction in library to use web based resources and services.

5.8 Satisfaction Level of Web Based Resources and Services: The findings of the designation-wise distribution of respondents satisfaction level of web based resources and services reveal that, 40.35 percent of the Professor respondent's, 40.57 percent of the Associate Professor respondents and 56.77 percent of the Assistant Professor respondents are satisfied. The findings of the gender-wise distribution of respondent's satisfaction level of web based resources reveal that, 52.17 percent of the male and 46.96 percent of the female respondents are satisfied about the utilization of web based resources and services.

5.9 Problems Faced While Accessing Web Based Resources and Services: The findings of the designation-wise distribution of respondents problems faced while accessing web based resources reveal that, 70.76 percent of the Professor respondent's, 61.24 percent of the Associate Professor respondent's and 65.44 percent of the

Assistant Professor respondents faced non availability of high end computers / network devices. The findings of the gender-wise distribution of respondents hindrances faced while accessing web based resources reveal that, 67.08 percent of the male respondent's and 75.00 percent of the female respondents faced non availability of high end computers / network devices.

5.10 Suggestion: The survey and the subsequent analysis of the data and the findings of the study have enabled the researchers to provide some practical suggestions for improving the web-based resources and services expected from study college libraries as follows:

- ✓ Every effort should be made on a consistent basis to update the websites frequently. This will certainly attract users to websites and then to the library resources and web-based library services.
- ✓ UGC of India with the help of INFLIBNET formulate the national web standards for library websites to meet the new challenges of next-generation web-based library and information architecture and set up web content steering committees to strengthen their controls on information.
- ✓ Adopt the next generation of the Internet (IPv6). In coming years, Internet and WWW will be the most important platform in academic learning environments.

6. Conclusion:

To sum up, this study throws light on the various aspects of web based resources and services usage among engineering professionals of SNSCE. E-journals service is the best used online services. Internet explorer is the most commonly used browser and Google is the most commonly used search engine among the users. User friendly is the main factor which influences the use of search engine. Users have undergone formal training to make best use of the resources. The study also suggests some measures to achieve effective and efficient use of web based resources and services by engineering professionals and research scholars.

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